

Mapping implementation challenges and solutions in a pregnancy cohort study on emerging infections in Honduras: A Pathfinder study

Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative studies (COREQ): 32-item checklist

Please indicate in which section each item has been reported in your manuscript. If you do not feel an item applies to your manuscript, please enter N/A.

For further information about the COREQ guidelines, please see Tong *et al.*, 2017:

<https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzm042>

No.	Item	Description	Section #
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity			
Personal characteristics			
1.	Interviewer/facilitator	Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group?	Methods, page 8
2.	Credentials	What were the researcher's credentials? <i>E.g. PhD, MD</i>	Methods, page 8
3.	Occupation	What was their occupation at the time of the study?	Methods, page 8
4.	Gender	Was the researcher male or female?	Methods, page 8
5.	Experience and training	What experience or training did the researcher have?	Methods, page 1
Relationship with participants			
6.	Relationship established	Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?	Methods, page 8
7.	Participant knowledge of the interviewer	What did the participants know about the researcher? <i>E.g. Personal goals, reasons for doing the research</i>	Methods, page 10
8.	Interviewer characteristics	What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator? <i>E.g. Bias, assumptions, reasons and interests in the research topic</i>	Methods, page 10
Domain 2: Study design			
Theoretical framework			
9.	Methodological orientation and theory	What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? <i>E.g. grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</i>	Methods, page 10
Participant selection			
10.	Sampling	How were participants selected? <i>E.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball</i>	Methods, page 10
11.	Method of approach	How were participants approached? <i>E.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email</i>	Methods, page 10
12.	Sample size	How many participants were in the study?	Methods, page 10
13.	Non-participation	How many people refused to participate or dropped out? What were the reasons for this?	Methods, page 10
Setting			

14.	Setting of data collection	Where was the data collected? <i>E.g. home, clinic, workplace</i>	Methods, page 11
15.	Presence of non-participants	Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?	Methods, page 10
16.	Description of sample	What are the important characteristics of the sample? <i>E.g. demographic data, date</i>	Methods, page 10
Data collection			
17.	Interview guide	Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?	Methods, page 10
18.	Repeat interviews	Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?	Methods, page 10
19.	Audio/visual recording	Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?	Methods, page 10
20.	Field notes	Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?	Methods, page 10
21.	Duration	What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?	Methods, page 10
22.	Data saturation	Was data saturation discussed?	
23.	Transcripts returned	Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?	NA
Domain 3: analysis and findings			
Data analysis			
24.	Number of data coders	How many data coders coded the data?	Methods, page 10
25.	Description of the coding tree	Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?	Methods, page 10
26.	Derivation of themes	Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?	Methods, page 10
27.	Software	What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data?	Methods, page 10
28.	Participant checking	Did participants provide feedback on the findings?	NA
Reporting			
29.	Quotations presented	Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings? Was each quotation identified? <i>E.g. Participant number</i>	Results, page 15
30.	Data and findings consistent	Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?	Results, page 13-16
31.	Clarity of major themes	Were major themes clearly presented in the findings?	Results, page 13-16
32.	Clarity of minor themes	Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes?	Discussion, page 15